

A Study on the Relationship between Child Behavior Management and Educator's Education

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Abstract

Confronting children about their behavior can have unintended and perhaps harmful effects on students and educators alike. Although successful tactics for behavior management can improve students' behavior, these strategies are not always faithfully applied in the classroom. The purpose of this exploratory mixed-method research is to explore what resources educators and other school personnel use to find information about effective behavior management strategies and their perceptions of these resources. The study will also explore what educators and other school personnel think of these resources (eg, search engines, internet media, professional organization websites, journals, peers, and professional development). In the interviews that followed, ten participants provided further insight into why educators chose certain tools and what they were looking for in behavioral resources. According to the findings, the most common reason for educators to consult their colleagues is that the information they give is easily accessible, understandable, reliable, and useful. The practice of challenging student behaviors such as disobedience, hostility, or deviation from the goal has detrimental effects on both children and educators. A decline in academic achievement, an increase in encounters with the juvenile justice system, and higher dropout rates have been associated with such behaviors (Gage & Macsuga-Gage, 2017; Noltemeyer et al., 2015; Rausch & Skiba, 2004). In addition, difficult student behaviors are one of the biggest contributors to teacher burnout and turnover rates (Brunsting et al., 2014; Garwood et al., 2018). Problems with behavior management are not specific to special education, as most teachers say that they must deal with children who exhibit difficult behaviors in their classrooms (Reinke et al., 2011; Westling, 2010). As a result, it is highly necessary for all

educators to create effective strategies for behavior control. This article is a review on the relationship between behavior management in children and education of the educator.

Keywords: *Behavior Management in Children, Education of the Educator, Relationship between Behavior Management in Children and Education of the Educator, Education in Children*

1. Introduction

It can be extremely important for teachers to use highly effective behavior-management strategies when working with children with special needs. This student demographic is most at risk for academic failure, drop-out, and expulsion (Bradley et al., 2008; Vaughn & Dammann, 2001). The use of effective behavior management strategies has been shown to lead to improvements in appropriate student behavior, engagement, and ultimately academic achievement (Scott, 2017; Simonsen et al., 2008). Unfortunately, most of the trainers' state that they do not receive adequate training on effective behavior-management strategies and are not equipped to cope with difficult behaviors (Freeman et al. 2014; Gable et al. 2012). Indeed, studies show that educators do not apply research-based practices consistently and faithfully (Burns & Ysseldyke, 2009; Gage et al., 2017; Hirn & Scott, 2014). In addition, educators frequently use some instructional and behavioral practices that are not supported or even refuted by research (Mostert, 2010). The gap between research and practice is problematic because the implementation of research-based practices in general leads to improved student outcomes, and the lack of these practices can have negative consequences for both students and educators. Therefore, it is of great importance that all children, especially those with disabilities or at risk of development, are educated by teachers who use behavioral approaches supported by research in their classrooms (Cook et al. 2016; Simonsen et al., 2008).

Carnine (1997) suggested that efforts to bridge the gap between research and practice will be hindered if educators perceive research evidence as unreliable, inaccessible, or unusable. Reliability refers to the level of trust educators place in research evidence. Accessibility refers to the ease with which research evidence can be obtained. Usability refers to the extent to which

CURRENT SCIENCE

research evidence can be applied. Carnine had theorized that educators had a general distrust of research because of the academic language contained in many study publications, as well as the carefully organized environments in which many studies were conducted. Boardman et al. (2005) discovered that a significant number of educators have a deep distrust of research. Educators have shown that they are more likely to trust information presented by their peers (also known as practice-based evidence) as opposed to evidence from research studies (Beahm & Cook, 2021, Boardman et al. Others, 2005; Smith et al., 2010). The second aspect that Carnine (1997) identifies is accessibility, which relates to how simple it is for educators to find and understand research on teaching approaches. Carnine noted the difficulties that teachers may encounter in finding and analyzing research papers (see also Vanderlinde & van Braak, 2010). Hudson et al. (2016), educators and administrators had difficulty accessing journal databases to retrieve research and in many cases were unsure how to access research. In addition, they may have difficulty understanding the findings of research studies, as most educators do not have extensive training in research and statistics. The third criterion Carnine (1997) considers is usability, which refers to the usefulness of the instructional content and whether educators believe they can act based on the information presented to them.

2. How a Specific Activity Should Be Implemented in a Classroom

Carnine stressed that study studies rarely make it clear how a particular activity should be implemented in a classroom setting. Landrum et al. (2007), educators found that reading about teaching methods from personal sources (such as a colleague) was more helpful than reading about teaching practices from data-driven sources (such as research published in a journal article). Similarly, Smith et al. (2010) discovered that educators reported finding information from other educators more helpful than information from a journal article . (“(PDF) Using Teacher Narratives in the Dissemination of ... - ResearchGate”) As a result, many educators do not believe that research is reliable, accessible, or useful. However, they see the instructional information received from their peers as more reliable, easily accessible, and useful. Due to the widespread use of social media platforms such as Pinterest and Teachers Pay Teachers, which emerged with the use of the

internet, teachers can now access their colleagues outside their own institutions. Emerging research reveals that many educators may be using social media sites like Teachers Pay Teachers and Pinterest to learn about teaching techniques. This may be the case because educators find information from other educators reliable, accessible, and useful (Opfer et al., 2016).

On the other hand, little is known about resources where educators can explore behavior management methods to help children with problem behavior. The aim of this study is to investigate which resources educators and other school personnel use to obtain information about effective behavior-management practices and to what extent they find these resources usable, reliable, understandable, applicable, and accessible. Additionally, the study will explore the extent to which educators and other school personnel use these resources to find information on effective behavior management practices.

3. Having a Range of Qualities and Talents

At this point in time, education is linked to the goal of transforming both people and society. To achieve this, the teacher must possess a set of qualities and abilities that enable him to provide a service aimed at achieving the set goal, which is the transformation of the individual into a successful professional. He is someone who can lead and lead a symphonic group. It should be noted that a teacher is a professional who aims to meet the specific need of the society at a given moment and provides a service to its users, a quality service to provide Peruvian holistic education. This fact should not be forgotten, because it is important to remember that a teacher is a professional who aims to meet the specific needs of society at a given moment. Jiménez (2013) discussed how emotions affect teacher-learning dynamics. According to the findings of this study, the primary component in determining a classroom environment is the interaction between the instructor and the students. This atmosphere has a positive or negative effect on students' learning capacities. He also argues that a negative emotional climate dominated by fear, insecurity, and anger does not allow students to react as expected and teachers do not provide appropriate information, so a negative emotional climate is perpetuated by violent behavior. Salinas (2014) investigated the link between the level of pedagogical management in high schools and the

CURRENT SCIENCE

teaching methods used there. In addition, he tried to identify the link that existed between methodological and instructional techniques and teacher practices. The findings indicate the existence of a significant link between the standard of pedagogical management and actual teaching action, which is highlighted in the results. Therefore, the researcher suggests that the population should prepare a methodological guide, considering the evaluation criteria and indicators that can be made, to evaluate the quality of pedagogical management and measure teaching practice in the classroom.

It emphasizes that pedagogical management at various levels of higher education and various professional degrees has become vital for solving the problems facing the educational process, considering current trends. Because it is vital to solve the problems faced by education professionals in the education process. This will reflect on students' academic success as well as their future professional development. We consider cognitive competence, procedural competence, attitudinal competence, and teaching competence, based on the many skills involved in pedagogical management. These competencies are summarized below. They play a crucial role when it comes to digesting new information and gaining knowledge throughout life. Thus, to know the effect of the first variable on the second variable, it is necessary to conduct research on the pedagogical management of teachers in relation to the instrumental performance of the symphonic group, recognizing that instrumental performance is a practical skill or ability.

This is because instrumental performance is a practical skill or ability that must be learned and directly demonstrated by students. This will allow it to be used in such future research work to enhance the practical learning acquired in the field of instrumental performance, while considering the continuing development of pedagogical management to achieve a quality professional education.

procedure would be perfect when the profile of the graduate in question is excellent. According to Montas (2008), the aim of quality education is to facilitate and follow the student in the teaching-learning process. This is done to encourage situations conducive to the generation of new knowledge as well as the development of the values and activities planned in the new curriculum. Pedagogical management is an effective tool for the work of teams and the school project, which

are the primary recipients of classroom teaching practice and continuing education for teachers. According to Espinel (2002) and Sevilla (2016), instrumental performance is defined as the act of performing a melody using a string, percussion, or wind instrument. To play an instrument, you will need certain things, including: an approach to the instrument, playing as you learn, musical notation, an understanding of how it sounds, and basic practice with the instrument. As defined by Leal (2010), instrumental performance is "an interpretation of any musical form on a particular academic or popular musical instrument in a variety of national and international scenarios." According to Aiello (2012), it is a method of self-expression through playing musical instruments; this allows students to develop and work on a variety of skills, as well as to develop an audio-visual motor coordination, thereby achieving values such as showing respect

Assessment of instrumental performance includes reading music, knowledge of music theory, knowledge of performance methods, and an understanding of how to play in an ensemble setting. Method Both descriptive and relational methods were used in the study.

4. Data Collection Tools

The following tools were used in the information collection process: The pedagogical management variable questionnaire for teachers consists of 20 open questions (Likert scale). These items evaluate teachers' cognitive, operational, attitudinal, and instructional competencies and provide information about teachers' pedagogical management. The rating scale and its corresponding index are used to classify the responses as follows.

Abbreviations, vocabulary, structures, and operations, as well as ways of being and ways of doing, as well as ways of being and doing had to be grasped by every researcher from the 40 nations involved in the project. We discussed, analyzed, and negotiated various definitions as we searched for common terminology and understandings of the work we were about to do. The most important of these was the concept of social justice. We have also studied, studied, and discussed numerous laws of social justice (Angelle, 2017, p. xvi). After performing the correlation analysis between the two factors, a very high correlation coefficient of 0.843 was discovered between the variable

CURRENT SCIENCE

representing the pedagogical management of the instructors and the variable representing the instrumental performance of the symphonic band. It was discovered that effective pedagogical management by instructors results in improved instrumental performance of the symphonic group, which allows students to achieve their educational goals. According to Montas (2008), the purpose of pedagogical management is to monitor and facilitate students in the teaching-learning process to encourage situations that support the development of new knowledge and values and activities planned in the new curriculum. In this context, pedagogical management is to monitor and facilitate students in the teaching-learning process. In the light of these findings, it is essential that the instructors have a comprehensive understanding of the subject and have the necessary skills to teach. According to Vázquez (2007), a teacher's cognitive competencies can primarily refer to the following professional practice areas: the area of relationship common to and with each student; the area of contact with other teachers, directives, and other professionals; it is the area of relationship with family and society, and lastly, the area of relationship with themselves. In conclusion, we can conclude that there is some significant level of linkage. Just as in the previous example, a moderate procedural proficiency was found to result in a moderate instrumental performance by the symphonic orchestra. Given this, pedagogical management by teachers should have a greater impact on students' hands-on learning as well as on the knowledge of strategies, techniques, skills, and methods easily transferred to students. According to Tobón (2006), knowing how to act in relation to the growth of an activity or the solution of a problem requires the use of planning as a basis and an understanding of the surrounding environment. In fact, two trends have emerged in recent years regarding how to structure ideal performance: The first involves an emphasis on learning and the learner, and, consequently, several ideas such as teaching people. Learning takes precedence over performance, which is ignored in this approach. Second, the focus is on growth rather than knowledge. It ignores information processing to focus on things like how effective and efficient something is, as well as how important it is to provide results that can be publicly reviewed. Based on such a finding, it is stated that strong management of social skills in the pedagogical management of teachers is necessary to build disposition and motivation, among other positive elements found in students that contribute to their instrumental performance. According to Pinto (2011) this competence is related to ethical considerations that guide and

CURRENT SCIENCE

provide meaning to both knowing and action. However, competency -based education is not limited to education that focuses on doing, but also includes education that focuses on knowing. As a result, theory, technique, and attitude must be considered harmoniously throughout the learning and teaching processes.

Therefore, it has been revealed that the use of teaching techniques in the classroom makes it possible to reach the appropriate level of learning in the instrumental performance of the symphonic band. According to Toledo (2006), teaching competence is defined as a teacher's ability to form a group social relationship between themselves and their students to perform an action outlined in a particular academic spatio-temporal schema.

In other words, teaching proficiency is a teacher's ability to form a relationship that can be understood by students. In other words, it is important how they recognize the knowledge, content and information that serve as a reference point and how they transform the acquired knowledge into agents(s) of change for their students. The management of classrooms, which includes both instructional and behavioral management, is an important issue for educators, school leaders, and system administrators as well as for the public.

It has a significant impact on how the community perceives events, how effective teachers feel and how well they feel overall, and how students do academically. These standards detail what teachers should know and be able to do and were developed to increase teacher effectiveness. The purpose of this study is to investigate the extent to which these requirements for teachers and early teacher education are consistent with each other in terms of successful classroom management knowledge and perspectives that can be found in the research literature .

It has been shown that educators, future educators, public education systems and students all have certain concepts in common with each other, but have many unique ideas (Hoy & Weinstein, 2006). While it is essential to determine the degree of coherence in ideas held by educators, students, and those entering the teaching profession, it is essential to identify knowledge and perspectives on effective classroom management, as well as knowledge and perspectives on “advice” discovered in the recent research literature . It is also important to determine to what extent the standards reflect this “recommendation”.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The term "creating positive learning environments" rather than "classroom management" is increasingly used in teacher education and by those interested in developing standards for teachers. This is because "classroom management" has negative connotations. Teachers have a responsibility to work towards creating conducive learning environments and should be able to recognize and improve classroom conditions that increase the likelihood of students engaging in such behavior (Hardman & Smith, 1999).

When teachers create environments of care in their classrooms, they create environments where potential challenges are planned, rules and consequences are established, classroom support is focused on positive behavior, and students are guided rather than scolded for behavior change. Various options are offered to achieve an agreed teaching goal. Positive classrooms are created when teachers' pay attention to all environmental cues present in educational settings (Banks, 2014).

Managing a classroom involves integrating many activities performed by the instructor to create, implement, and maintain a productive learning environment. This new definition encompasses a range of tasks, including: developing caring and supportive relationships with and between students while maintaining high and open expectations; organize and implement teaching that facilitates deep and meaningful learning and encourages student engagement; promoting the development of students' social skills and self-regulation to help students articulate challenges and find solutions ; and using appropriate interventions to help students clarify challenges and find solutions (McDonald 2013, Weinstein, 2006). "Clearly, managing students in a classroom is a multidimensional effort that is much more involved in regulating students' behavior than setting rules, incentives, and punishments" (Weinstein, 2006, p. 5). Evertson and Weinstein (2006) provide a definition of classroom management that is often quoted. Classroom management, by their definition, "consists of activities undertaken by instructors to create an atmosphere that fosters and encourages both academic and social-emotional development, not only academic learning, but also aims to increase the social and moral development of students." it does not just aim to create and maintain an orderly environment". Because students come from a wide variety of backgrounds, interests, and ability levels, meeting their needs, and engaging them in meaningful learning requires careful planning and dexterity. However, according to McDonald, this organized learning

CURRENT SCIENCE

environment can only truly be achieved when teachers understand their own needs as well as their students and work together to meet those needs. It offers a Positive Learning Framework (PLF) that highlights the strengths they have and how teachers as educators can leverage those strengths to help all children develop further. This framework is based on the latest research in positive psychology as well as resilience, self-worth, and neurological research. The Professional Learning Framework (PLF) provides a range of behaviors for teachers, from planning and preventive methods to strategies for instructional design and response to student behavior. If teachers learn to successfully apply their assigned talents, they can create high-quality learning environments characterized by strong teacher-student connections (McDonald, 2013). More recently, education policies and research conducted during the previous 10 years have led educators towards more empirical approaches that are empirically and scientifically supported (Hattie, 2009). Simonsen, Fairbanks, Briesch, and Myers (2008) conducted an empirical literature review to identify evidence-based classroom management approaches and found a total of five strategies.

"Classroom management practices were considered evidence-based if they met the following criteria :

- (a) a robust experimental design and methodology (group experimental, group quasi-experimental, experimental single-subject designs, or causal comparative).*
- (b) effective and*
- (c) empirical studies published in peer-reviewed journals " (pp. 352-353).*

Several different tactics and general practices were discovered that could be categorized as "evidence-based" and were later brought together as the five most important aspects of successful classroom management.

- 1. Maximize structure by making use of instructor-led activities, clearly defined routines, and physical classroom organization in terms of adequate space between row sets and visual screens.*
- 2. Setting expectations and teaching social skills, reminding students of appropriate behavior in the classroom, by identifying and defining a small number of positively worded*

CURRENT SCIENCE

rules or agreements and then making sure they are well taught, modeled, reviewed, and supervised by the teacher by walking around the room, interacting with students, and to direct.

3. Apply a wide variety of teaching methods to reduce the number of disruptive behaviors occurring in the classroom and encourage student engagement.

4. To do this, accept appropriate behavior using a variety of tactics that focus on identifying and recognizing good classroom behavior, using both individual and group support.

5. Responding to inappropriate behavior in a variety of ways, including low-key approaches to remembering and guiding behavior, deliberate ignoring, and rational responses, among other options. According to these studies, "answers that are direct, rapid, and result in the student giving the correct answer were most successful in increasing future success rates" (Simonsen, Fairbanks, Briesch, Myers & Sugai, 2008, p. 365).

As the findings of the study conducted by De Jong (2005) to determine what constitutes best practice in Australian schools, it is a difficult task to determine what constitutes good classroom management and what does not. According to De Jong's findings, a significant portion of the methods considered best practice "lack of 'hard' evidence to support claims of beneficial results" (2005, p. 357). Most of the programs reviewed for this research (70%) used anecdotal evidence, but only 20% of the programs were properly reviewed (some were under evaluation). However, there were emerging signs that effective techniques depended on contributing factors as well as beliefs. The aim of the project was to design a set of guiding principles and practices that could be used to facilitate the creation of more appropriate methods for regulating behavior in classrooms, schools, and districts. The research was primarily driven by two important questions: what constitutes best practice in addressing student behavior and what are the key concepts in treating student behavior problems. De Jong surveyed six to ten programs in each of three school jurisdictions, Catholic, State, and Independent, and used a literature review on best practices in Australian schools to look for connections and overlap . De Jong thought something was good practice when the literature repeatedly referred to certain aspects and surveys confirmed this. "For

CURRENT SCIENCE

the purposes of this project, best practice has been interpreted as strategies associated with philosophy, policy, organizational structure and culture, procedure , development and action that are likely to result in successful addressing of student behavior issues."

It has been interpreted as strategies related to best practice, philosophy, policy, organizational structure and culture, procedure , development in line with the objectives (De Jong, 2005, p. 356). The discovery that led to improvement This framework revealed seven key principles and practices for managing student behavior. These principles and practices are a synthesis of many key elements explored as part of interactionist and authoritarian movements. It is called the "ecosystemic perspective," which emphasizes the complex interaction that exists between environmental, interpersonal, and personal components. An article to look beyond behavior to understand motivations and influences in play, and that students' behavior is influenced by both the context in which they learn and others, including teachers, and that it is necessary to address both the problematic environment and problematic behavior . This suggests that a "one size fits all" approach may not really work, and adaptive and personalized learning environments may be necessary for some children.

5. Safe, Encouraging, and Compassionate Situations

The concept of health, a method that is beneficial to one's health and aims to create safe, stimulating, and compassionate situations, is broken down into its components:

Physical, cognitive, social, emotional, and spiritual domains.

These spaces work together to provide safe learning environments that promote healthy behaviors. It is about engagement with established pastoral care institutions that take a proactive rather than reactive stance towards the issues at hand. It is not a pattern of deficiency that needs to be corrected; rather, it is a pattern of behavior at risk that needs to be guided. The aim is to create an environment where behavior is seen as part of diversity. The associated best practice is very similar to the best practice recommended in the tiered approach of Positive Behavior Supports (PBS), but also includes addressing student needs through a case management strategy and providing individual

attention as needed. This ensures that children and parents who are going through a difficult time regarding their children's behavior have access to a variety of mental health resources available in the community as well as at school. While De Jong's work highlights feature previously highlighted by Simonsen and others. (2008) underlined the need for in-depth knowledge and understanding of young people, their needs and the factors influencing their behavior. Simonsen et al. While describing the basic methods for successful classroom management, De Jong (2005) emphasized beliefs and knowledge in addition to practice within the basic principles mentioned. Both groups of researchers focused on identifying techniques for good classroom management. The research on teachers' and pre-service teachers' beliefs about classroom management (Brophy, 1998; Flowerday & Shaw, 2000; Lyons & O'Connor, 2006; Woolfolk Hoy & Weinstein, 2006) clearly reveals teachers' and prospective teachers' beliefs about classroom management. reveals. -service teachers need continuing education and support in the use of effective classroom management strategies, but also the identification and development of attitudes and beliefs that are consistent with current research on teacher effectiveness, which includes linking both teaching and learning (Jong, 2005, p. 359).

6. Efficiency of Teaching in the Classroom and Instructional Leadership

The atmosphere in the classroom is strongly influenced by the teaching staff. Research on the factors that influence student behavior and learning consistently points to the effectiveness of instructors as a critical component, although student learning is affected by a wide variety of circumstances. According to Hattie (2003), the solution to the problem of how to improve outcomes for all students "lies in the person who gently closes the door of the classroom and performs the teaching act. Who interprets these policies and who is left alone with students during their 15,000-hour education" Explained by not being the first person to point out the significant impact they can have on their students? The importance of a good educator is often highlighted as a key finding in studies of resilience. Werner and Smith (1989) state that children's favorite teachers are among the most common positive role models in children's lives. they discovered that.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The methods or approaches teachers use in their classrooms can yield a collection of best practices we can use to guide our work in schools and classrooms. However, like many aspects of teaching practice, an individual's ideas about young people, their needs, the behaviors they exhibit, and the factors that influence those behaviors often drive our actions. "The type of education and discipline we have in schools and classrooms is determined by our philosophical beliefs about teaching, learning, and the students themselves" (Freiberg, 1999, p.14) . This type of definition is extremely limiting, framing teacher effectiveness as a teacher's ability to produce gains in students' learning (as reflected in standardized test scores), although it has some credibility since most people would agree that a teacher's role is to assist students in learning, does not require a certain amount of persuasiveness. has.

7. Conclusion

There are many more ways that teachers can contribute to the success of their students, communities, and schools, but these are sometimes neglected (Goe, Bell, & Little, 2008). To find a working definition of successful teaching, Goe, Bell, and Little (2008) scanned the most recent academic literature and analyzed a wide range of topics covered in policy documents, standards, and reports. They concluded that effective teachers have high expectations for all students and help students learn. They contribute to positive academic, attitudinal, and social outcomes for all students; they use resources to plan and structure engaging learning opportunities. ("Teaching Effectiveness Definition - 776 Words - Internet Public Library") They contribute to the development of classrooms and schools that value diversity and civic awareness, and collaborate with other teachers, administrators, parents, and education professionals to ensure students receive an appropriate education. Reading research on teacher competence offers a more complex and nuanced perspective. According to Campbell, Kyriakides, Muijs, and Robinson (2003), "teacher effectiveness" is defined as "the effect of classroom characteristics such as teaching techniques, teacher expectations, classroom organization and use of classroom resources on students' performance". Examining the teaching models that define what effective teachers know and do, as well as the behaviors that effective teachers incorporate into their practice, is one way to

understand the effectiveness of teaching. For example, we can see that many more standards have a very important relationship with the effective (2013) understanding and implementation. Jacob Kounin recommended in 1970 that the strategies needed for effective classroom management are the same as those needed to create an effective classroom ecology and learning environment. This advice still applies today. Acquiring and mastering many approaches gives us the ability to perform a wide variety of tasks. A more coherent understanding of knowledge and insights has developed because of analyzing research on successful classroom management and integrating it into effective teaching frameworks, notably the AITSL standards . Successful classroom management involves much more than just enforcing rules and distributing rewards and punishments and having a solid understanding of classroom management techniques is not an end. Consequently, this knowledge and understanding should inform beginning teacher programs in their approach to teaching classroom management effectively.

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